

Synthesis of Antidiabetic Sulphonylurea Compounds

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Sulphonylurea derivatives of the general formula, $p\text{-R-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NHCONH-R}'$ (where R is amino, alkyl, or halogen and R' is alkyl group) possess remarkable antidiabetic properties. Such compounds introduced into medicine are carbutamide (R=NH₂; R'=CH₃.CH₂.CH₂.CH₂-), tolbutamide (R=CH₃; R'=CH₃.CH₂.CH₂.CH₂-) and chlorpropamide (R=Cl; R'=CH₃.CH₂.CH₂-). In this paper a general and commercially successful method for the synthesis of this type of compound is described.

The benzenesulphonamide derivative ($p\text{-R-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-SO}_2\text{NH}_2$) is heated with equimolecular proportion of potassium cyanate in alcoholic solution for several hours when potassium salt of the sulphonylurea ($p\text{-R-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NHCONH}_2$) is obtained. On acidification in aqueous solution it furnishes the pure sulphonylurea compound which on heating with the hydrochloride of the alkylamine (R'-NH₂) in non-aqueous solvent for several hours affords the required sulphonylurea derivative of the general formula, $p\text{-R-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NHCO-NH-R}'$. These are obtained as colorless crystals from dilute methanol or ethanol, melting with decomposition.

Carbutamide (*p-Aminobenzenesulphonylbutylurea*).—*p-Aminobenzenesulphonamide* (1 mol.) and potassium cyanate (1 mol.) were heated in ethanolic solution for several hours under reflux. On cooling, a crystalline mass separating was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried, again dissolved in water at room temperature, and filtered. When the filtrate was acidified in cold with dilute hydrochloric acid, *p-aminobenzenesulphonylurea* separated. This was collected, washed, and crystallised from water in colorless needles, m.p. 144-45° (decomp). (Found N, 19.08. C₇H₉O₃N₃S requires N, 19.53%). *p-Aminobenzenesulphonylurea* (1 mol.) and butyl^{1a} amine hydrochloride (1.2 mol.) were heated in ethanolic solution for several hours under reflux. About half the alcohol was then distilled and the residue was diluted with water in cold when *p-aminobenzenesulphonylbutylurea* separated in a semi-solid state. This was collected and washed with cold water, dissolved in 10% NaOH solution, treated with charcoal in cold and filtered. The filtrate was acidified in cold with dilute hydrochloric acid when the compound separating was collected, washed with cold water, and crystallised from dilute methanol in colorless needles, m. p. 140-41° (decomp). (Found: N, 15.41; C₁₁H₁₇O₃S requires N, 15.49%).

Tolbutamide (*p-methylbenzenesulphonylbutyl^{1a} urea*) was similarly prepared by taking *p-methylbenzenesulphonamide* instead of *p-aminobenzenesulphonamide* and obtained

ed as colorless needles from dilute ethanol, m.p. 127-29° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.30. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 10.37%).

Chlorpropamide (*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonylpropylⁿ urea) was also similarly prepared from *p*-chlorobenzenesulphonamide and propylⁿamine hydrochloride and obtained as colorless needles from dilute ethanol; m. p. 127-29° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.23. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 10.12%).

The yields at every stage of the reactions are very high.

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Sri N. Adhikari, **Manager**, Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical works, for his interest in this work.

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Received February 22, 1961.